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Flow of Knowledge

Our economic prosperity depends on two pillars: the universities and the manufacturing industry. While the universities are responsible for education and innovation, the industry has to ensure the necessary profit, which in turn allows the governments to finance the universities. It is important that innovation knowledge flows seamlessly from universities to industries, and should not be interrupted when an expert involved enters a new phase of her or his life.

Phases of Life

Let us divide our life into three phases: phase P1 are the first 30 years, the years of education, followed by phase P2, our active job years, and finally by phase P3 when we retire at the age of 65. But between them we have to master phase transitions, which from P1 to P2 means to find a satisfying job, to learn running a business and to take responsibility for employees. Such a change is often accompanied by some kind of *culture shock*, especially when you have to concentrate on daily business issues and no longer on innovations. The second phase transition from P2 to P3 is even more frustrating, when suddenly you are no longer responsible for business decisions. Then the knowledge flow from research to industry in the first case is obviously faltering, and in the second case, from industry into private life, valuable knowledge may even get lost.

It makes sense – also from a national-economical point of view – to create some kind of institutions between the phases to damp the personal culture shock and to avoid the loss of expertise. Suitable instruments in the first interface are the well-know start-up companies, and those for the second one we will call roll-out companies.

Start-Ups

Let us consider those start-ups which are located close to universities, founded and driven by Post Docs. Their aim is to transfer verified research results into first market products. The innovative power of start-ups is high, but there is usually little or no business experience, thus the risk of failure is relatively high. Special agencies as *Innosuisse* provide best support in business coaching to survive the first critical years.

Roll-Outs

It makes sense to keep access to the experts' know-how when they become retired. Some companies ask retired colleagues to take care of patents, or offer to be members of a taskforce to solve unexpected internal problems. But this is psychologically critical, and retired experts should better look for options to continue their creativity, and to this purpose the setting up of an own company for a limited period of time is an attractive possibility.

Golden Rules to run a Roll-Out Firm

- It is a fact that you only can keep your professionalism in your previous working field. The difference is that you are now free to think about applications outside the business view of your former company that are attractive and challenging. The advantages of an own firm, such as a GmbH¹, are the deduction of investment and operating costs from tax, and the limited liability for risks up to a certain harmless amount of money.
- But don't be too innovative! Customers and their companies are only interested in new applications or products as long as they can be understood and managed by the their internal marketing and sales organizations.
- Your personal network is important, since contacts to companies must always go top/down. But no top manager will decide against his experts. This is probably the most difficult psychological barrier to penetrate the ‚clay layer‘ of middle management, who don't like external ideas.
- Concerning your own roll-out firm: try to minimize fixed costs. Instead of keeping a permanent staff, a loose network of retired colleagues is optimum. The team comes together when required and is paid on a time basis. Communication takes place virtually, so your experts can be spread all over the world. Such a cooperation can be very efficient, and even complex tasks can be professionally solved in a very short time, as will be shown next.
- Try to offer working demonstrators or even prototypes to your customer by cooperating with an institute of a FHS² or a specialized SME. A demonstrator is the best way to convince the middle management that your idea can be further developed to industrial maturity by them.

Example: Neutron Microscope

Our team of freelancers for lens design, coatings, mechanical construction and production technology was asked by a group at PSI some years ago to develop a special optics for neutron microscopy. While in X-ray imaging metallic objects can be detected inside organic materials, it is the opposite case when using neutrons, as it allows to visualize e.g organic objects inside a metallic housing.

To this purpose the object is illuminated by a collimated beam of thermal/cold neutrons and its cast shadow is projected onto a thin scintillator crystal. The resulting fluorescence pattern is imaged onto a CCD-array with a high-performance microscopic lens (Fig. 1). Our team finished the complicated optic design within few months, including the intensive discussions of the manufacturing tolerance settings with a potential optics supplier.

¹ Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung (Limited liability company)

² Fachhochschule, University of Applied Science

Figure 1: Optical microscope to image the fluorescence light on a CCD from a neutron stimulated Gd target.

The challenge for the optical layout is that even if the objective is placed outside the incident neutron beam, a certain exposure of the optical components by strayed neutrons can not be excluded. Since the optical design of the objective showed tight tolerance values for the glass materials, there must be certainty to what extent the refractive indices can change over a working period of 5 to 10 years by the neutron impact.

Technical Details

The cold or thermal neutrons after having penetrated the object under test are registered by a special target sensor, using the fact that cold neutrons are strongly absorbed by the rare earth element gadolinium ¹⁵⁷Gd. The neutron excitation causes fluorescence in the green spectral range. The scintillator target sensor is a 2D-array of 2000 light pipes of 5 μm diameter, doped with Gd. The telecentric objective with F-No = 1.25 images the Gd-target of size 10 × 10 mm² onto a CCD of size 50 × 50 mm², characterized by a P43 spectral Illumination profile. Details of the project including system aspects can be found in ³ (Fig. 2).

Glasses

If a glass is exposed to radioactive radiation as in space projects, so-called radiation-resistant glasses must be used instead of normal glasses. They are stabilized by the addition of cerium oxide. There is a lot of experience with high-energy particles or gamma radiation, but less with neutrons.

The reason is that thermal neutrons are strongly absorbed by the isotope Borium ¹⁰B, which is as B₂O₃ an important component of many optical glasses. The glasses turn brown under neutron irradiation by the reaction ¹⁰B(n,α)⁷Li producing α-particles of about 2.3 MeV, but even worse, the re-

³ Progress in High-resolution Neutron Imaging at the Paul Scherrer Institut – The Neutron Microscope Project, Pavel Trtik, Eberhard H. Lehmann, Neutron Imaging & Activation Group, Laboratory for Neutron Scattering & Imaging, Paul Scherrer Institut, CH-5232 Villigen PSI, Switzerland, VI European Conference on Neutron Scattering (ECNS2015) IOP Publishing, Journal of Physics: Conference Series 746 (2016) 012004 doi:10.1088/1742-6596/746/1/012004

Figure 2: Schematic of cross-sectional view of the PSI Neutron Microscope showing (from right to left): the sample holder (pink), adaptor with the scintillator screen (green and yellow), the dedicated magnifying objective composed of 13 individual lenses (light grey), and a CCD detector (red and black).

fractive indices will change. Since it was unclear to which amount this would happen, the risk of radiation damage had to be minimized by the optics design. First the objective was placed outside and perpendicular to the incident neutron beam, which led to a minimum distance between Gd sensor and front lens element of 60 mm, and to a free diameter of the first lens of 76 mm. (Fig. 2) This resulted in a large construction size of the optics, and to the tight tolerance values already mentioned. Since neutrons are also scattered at the object under test, we chose as second step *fused silica* as material for the first three lenses, which is also radiation resistant for neutrons. For the following lenses, however, one needed different glass materials to achieve apochromasy.

Since PSI estimated a neutron flux of 10⁷/(cm²·s) (including 10% scattering at the target) at their location of the sample, which would lead to a fluence of $\Phi = 6.3 \cdot 10^{14}$ cm² for a service life of 10 years, assuming 20% under beam exposure, the third step of our optical layout was to select for the remaining lenses boron free glass material ⁴.

However, it was surprising that some glasses of our first design as N-LAF2, N-LAK22, N-SK16, N-PSK3 from SCHOTT contained up to 20 weight% of B₂O₃ (Fig. 3). As it could not be excluded that the objective type would also be used at other neutron locations with stronger neutron intensities and larger beam diameters, we decided as third step to redesign the objective using glasses that were low in boron oxid as N-SK2 and N-BAK2 with maximum 4.8 weight% of B₂O₃.

The absorption of thermal neutrons by borium produces α-particles of about 2.3 MeV by the reaction ¹⁰B(n,α)⁷Li. The absorption cross section is $\sigma_{WQ} = \mu(^{10}\text{B}) \cdot 3837 \text{ barns} = 768 \text{ barns}$ using the isotope abundance factor $\mu(^{10}\text{B}) = 0.2$ (Fig. 4) ⁵.

Then the absorption constant in N-BK7 is $k_{N-BK7} = \sigma_{WQ} \cdot N_{Vol} = \sigma_{WQ} \cdot \eta_1 \cdot \eta_2 \cdot \rho_{N-BK7} \cdot N / A(B)$, using the Avogadro-Constant $N = 6.02 \cdot 10^{23}$ /Mol. The atomic weight of borium is $A = 10.8 \text{ g/Mol}$ leading to $\eta_1 = A(B_2) / A(B_2O_3) = 21.6 \text{ g} / 69.6 \text{ g} = 0.31$. The factor $\eta_2 = 0.14$ describes that N-BK7 includes

⁴ Private communication of E. H. Lehmann (PSI), 18.02.2014

⁵ Precision Determination of the Slow Neutron Absorption Cross Section of B10, G. J. Safford, T. I. Taylor, B. M. Rustad, and W. W. Havens, Jr., Phys. Rev. 119, 1291 – Published 15 August 1960

Figure 3: Abbe Diagram, indicating the amount of B_2O_3 in optical glasses (Private communication of P. Hartmann, SCHOTT AG, 25.2.2014)

about 14 weight% B_2O_3 , and $\rho_{N-BK7} = 2.5 \text{ g/cm}^3$ is the density. This leads to $k_{N-BK7} = 768 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 0.31 \cdot 0.14 \cdot 2.5 \text{ g/cm}^3 \cdot 6 \cdot 10^{23} / 10.8 \text{ g} = 4.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The neutron intensity ratio $I(d) / I(0) = \exp(-k_{N-BK7} \cdot d)$ would drop to 50% for $d_{0.5} = -\ln(0.5) / k_{N-BK7} = 1.5 \text{ mm}$. This is in good agreement with experiments at PSI-SINQ which showed a transmission loss of approximately 50% of a 1.8 mm thick glass disc made of borosilicate glass N-BK7 when irradiated with a neutron fluence of $5.7 \cdot 10^{15} / \text{cm}^2$. A 10 mm thick glass plate made of N-SK16 with a boron content of 19.3 weight% would be sufficient to shield the objective (Fig. 1).

Part of the lens design work was to discuss the design, including the tolerances for components and assembly, with potential suppliers in Switzerland, the Czech Republic and Germany. This includes the mechanical accuracy specifications (centering angles, glass thicknesses, air gaps) and narrower specifications of the optical glass parameters such as refractive indices and dispersion values. Here it became apparent that the companies investing in modern production technology allowed tighter mechanical tolerances in order to be able to accept standard glass tolerances. This gave them a cost advantage when submitting tenders.

6 Private communication of E. H. Lehmann (PSI), 15.07.2013

Figure 4: Absorption cross factor σ_{wq} of borium isotopes as function of neutron energy.